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Growth and development of higher educational institutions in India with especial reference to science education in the late 19th and early decade 20th centuries.

To believe that the British colonizers were only responsible for improving India's educational infrastructure would be erroneous. It is well-documented that India had an established education system for the sciences and the arts by the Middle Ages. The fact that people from all over the world traveled to India to attend institutions like Taxila and Nalanda is proof enough of how far ahead of the curve Indian education was. However, the arrival of the British in India altered how new information was acquired. They carried their expertise with them and used it to build massive infrastructure. England's industrial revolution gave rise to a new scientific and technological landscape that contrasted with the colonies. As a result, educational institutions grounded on colonial science grew and flourished, with British scientific knowledge systems taking center stage. To learn what drove the expansion of these organizations in the latter part of the nineteenth century and the first two decades of the twentieth century, we will examine this phenomenon below.

The Phases

The Company Act of 1792 laid the legal groundwork for the modernization of India's educational system under British control. That which has only begun to take shape might be thought of as the embryonic stages of India's education strategy. Several high-ranking British officials, like Charles Grant and William Wilberforce, were keen on spreading helpful education and information to the Indian population. They submitted a bill to the House of Commons in Britain. Some members of the Board of Directors were critical, though. They were not enthusiastic about providing free education to thousands of Indians. Probably out of concern that was interfering in subjects like education might affect their political and economic operations negatively, the Government ultimately withheld aid for another twenty years.

Among the British officials interested in opening an education system of their kind, besides Charles Grant and Wilberforce, were Warren Hastings, Jonathan Duncan, and Micheal Topping, who founded some institutions to promote Education among Indians. However, the main subject of education was not 'science.' Instead, it was ethics and moral education. One can see the 'White Man's Burden' theory in practice. "Christianity, not science, was the main source of that 'light and knowledge.' Thus, for a long time, the diffusion of more important and useful learning in sciences did not come up even in the debates throughout this phase."

Even in the case of the orientalist, the main objective of setting up institutions like the *Hindu Sanskrit College of Benaras* and the *Calcutta Madrassa* was the promotion of educating the Indians on their religious law and order and to ease the administration for the British since this would ensure a regular supply of qualified Muslim and Hindu law officers in the Judicial system.

By 1813, the Company Government had officially recognized education as a state topic. As a result, the transition into the next stage may commence. Interestingly, the Company Government, which did little to promote education in more practical branches of science, took the lead in disseminating Sanskrit literature and Oriental Science. They went as far as recommending that prospective professors be chosen from among Indians who may have some knowledge of eastern science. During the second phase, however, there was a growing clamor among some segments of Indian society for introducing an educational system grounded in western scientific principles. British colonial expansion and maintenance in India necessitated educating indigenous Indian youngsters in Western ways. As a result, it was inevitable that the United Kingdom would actively promote its scientific, mathematical, and medical achievements.

Lord Macaulay's appointment as head of the Committee of Public Instruction in 1834 marked the beginning of the third and most significant phase in the evolution of India's educational system. But first, let's talk about the 1830s' heated debate between Orientalists and Anglicists. Promoting European Science and literature in India was made more accessible by the Charter Act of 1813. However, the Court of Directors' first directives emphasized expanding eastern literature. The Public Instruction Committee supported the orientalist's vision of a synthesis of indigenous and European pedagogy, as well as the dissemination of European Science and

literature via vernacular mediums. H.T. Prinsep advocated vigorously for disseminating European scientific knowledge into Indian languages. He inferred that this was the "one strategy that has any chance of producing widespread improvement in population in Scientific and Ethical Values." William Carey said, "whatever goals else could be met by establishing the English language among Indians, the prospect of giving competent teaching to them or indeed any people in a language not their own is entirely erroneous." The linguist's mission aimed to improve the efficiency of the British authorities by familiarising them with the local language and culture. In 1800, this need was seen as the driving force for establishing Port William College in Calcutta. The second reason was to learn about and foster relationships with the indigenous community's elite. These goals were primarily responsible for the foundation of Calcutta Madrassa and the Benaras Sanskrit College. The General Committee gave in to the orientalist's demands and came up with a strategy to translate certain key European publications on science into local languages. There is a confident Dr. Tyler who is in charge of this project.

On the other hand, the Anglicists were dead set against both the dissemination of knowledge about eastern science and literature and the use of vernacular languages to spread knowledge about Europe. C.E. Trevelyan, the Committee's principal spokesperson, argued that the language "keeps erroneous systems which have been exploded for two or three centuries past and impede their adoption of the most advanced system of learning which the world has yet to witness." At this point, the Board of Directors had already altered its mind and was saying, "the higher fields of sciences may be more profitably studied in the languages of Europe than in translations into eastern languages." But "the open, professed, and dominant purpose of the British Government in India until March 1835 continued to be the advancement of eastern literature and science." Middle-class Indians became more vocal in their desire for exposure to European Science and education, but they were met with resistance from a significant faction within the Company Government. According to their analysis, it "is too soon to focus all our efforts on producing engineers and chemists as a profession. Currently, there is either zero or a little demand for them."

TB Macaulay, the president of the Committee of Public Instruction, was an Anglican. His advocacy for expanding access to "English Education" in India was unwavering. Knowledge, ethics, and the scientific and literary achievements of

Europe fascinated him. William Bentinck, India's former governor general, advocated for the western education system.

Technical Education

Pressure to expand access to STEM education among Indians grew steadily during the last several years. As a result, many standalone establishments were established in the final stage. The idea of training a second-rate class of civil engineers among the Indians dates back to 1840 when it was devised to aid the European engineer in expanding the scope of his activities. Madras High School (1842), Hindu College (1843), and Elphinstone College (1845) all made efforts to provide engineering courses (1844). However, their efforts were fruitless. However, the British Government had an immediate need for Indian civil engineers. The construction of roads, the metaling of highways, bridges, irrigation canals, water mill facilities, the introduction of railroads, and the completion of surveys all needed the application of engineering knowledge. In September 1847, Thomason proposed establishing a school of engineering in Roorkee. On October 5, 1847, the idea was accepted by Lord Dalhousie, and on January 1, 1848, the orders were issued. Sub-assistant Executive Engineers, Overseers, Assistant Overseers, and the third class of local Youths for the subordinate branch of engineering and surveying were all eligible for free tuition at Roorkee Civil Engineering College. Thomason College of Civil Engineering was established there in 1854 and afterward renamed after its namesake. Students were taken to building sites and other public works projects to see and learn from the professionals at work. The enormous needs of the Bengal presidency were beyond the capabilities of Thomason College. Students from the North-Western Provinces were not preferred for jobs in Lower Bengal. Since they had no prior exposure to Bengali culture, language, or weather. Lahore's Board of Directors was not particularly enthusiastic about hiring Bengals, and students from that region were hesitant to study engineering in the Upper Provinces.

Lord Dalhousie understood that the presidency of Bengal required more than a single institution. He suggested the Goodwins Plan as a result. In the Writers' Building, the Calcutta College of Civil Engineering was founded after the Court of Directors authorized the Plan on May 2, 1855.

The provision for founding engineering schools lagged a little behind in the other presidencies, such as Madras and Bombay. The long-planned Civil Engineering College in Madras did not open until 1858. Poona College was the only institution in the Bombay presidency to produce highly-qualified Math and English majors consistently. Under these administrations, efforts to expand access to engineering education have moved at a snail's pace. It's possible that other areas of science and technology education took a back seat to the development of ports, commerce, and railroads. In 1855, the East Indian Railway Company set up a training facility to prepare Indians for careers in the railroad industry. The majority of Indian workers, however, were engaged in manual labor and mechanical roles. Their instruction did not include other parts of the 'difficult tasks.'

Dr. W.B. O'Shaughnessy, India's Superintendent of Electric Telegraphs, established four telegraph reading schools for local youngsters in the cities of Bengal, Agra, and Madras.

The possibility of establishing Calcutta Mechanical Institutions was also discussed. The Military Board proposed integrating theoretical and practical mathematics instruction. Thanks to Goodwin's efforts, the School of Industrial Arts in Calcutta was founded that year. With the support of local Rajas, W. Taylor, the Commissioner of Patna Division, proposed the establishment of an industrial institute in Bihar. And Zamindars. Sir Jamsetjee Jeejeebhoy founded Bombay's School of Art and Industry in 1856.

Natural Science Education

The British needed to study and examine the accessible physical aspects of the environment to comprehend and deal with the prevailing circumstances. This means the British place a premium on botany, agriculture, veterinary science, geology, and mining fields. The business actively supported academic research into India's unique plant and animal life. Botany courses, notably in Bengal, were cut or eliminated from universities. After arriving in Calcutta in 1873, George Watts was requested to teach chemistry rather than botany. It was urged that Richard Temple drop botany from his curriculum. He didn't get rid of it but cut down on how often it was taught. The botany programs at Patna and Rajshahi were shut down. Elimination of it occurred at Hughli University. Allen Croft, the DPI, pushed to keep the interviewee. But his pleas were ignored, and the GOI scrapped the courses, using the customary excuse

of "no actual demand." Forestry relied heavily on botany. The Government of India approved D Brandis's plan to establish Central Forest School at Dehra Dun in 1878.

Despite being the most significant landowner in the world, the British Government disregarded scientific advice on farming for decades. Throughout the 1860s, representatives from the Landholders' organization and the British Indian association sought education like this periodically, but authorities merely gave lip service. Robertson, who was in charge of the Saidapet Agricultural Farm, was adamant about establishing an agricultural college, and in 1876 he finally succeeded. It was suggested that the Patna College of Bihar add an agriculture college. A subject in agriculture was first offered in 1879 at Poona Civil Engineering College. By the following year, studies in agriculture had also been added to the curriculums of six of the top Zilla schools in the Bombay Presidency, thanks to the efforts of Richard Temple. Mamlatdars and Karkuns, native revenue officials, also sprang to mind as potential agents for this task. farmers' expertise and the desire to see a degree program in agriculture established at Bombay University. However, only diploma requirements are required by the institution.

It was in 1890 that the GOI held a Conference for Agriculture, with Dr. Voelckers's help and encouragement. In 1897, the Imperial Government suggested constructing four high classes in colleges in Madras, Bombay, Calcutta, and several other towns in northern India because agricultural colleges provided adequate training for state officials in land revenues and associated activities.

Training veterinarians was crucial for the success of agricultural economies and the well-being of the military's equine units. For military purposes, the Poona College of Science began offering veterinary courses in the middle of the 1880s. In 1886, the veterinary college in Bombay was the first in the world to provide classes in English using a purely European model of education. However, enrollment dropped dramatically that year, from 80 pupils the year before to only 42. A new debate on the need for veterinary education was sparked when the Calcutta business sector established pinjarapole (an animal asylum) in 1890. A veterinary college opened in 1893 in Calcutta. It took three years for it to become a university. Veterinary schools in Madras and Calcutta struggled to find success. However, the service was superior in Lahore and Ajmer. Captain Trydell, head of Bengal's Civil Veterinary

Department, says, "*All of Lahore's pupils are from the zamindar class; the vast majority are Muhammaddans, who are raised around and trained to care for animals, and a sizeable proportion are sowars from Native Cavalry Regiments. In contrast, only a tiny percentage of Bengali applicants can ride or have any experience with animals; many are first too afraid even to approach a horse*".

It's safe to say that the fields of geology and mining played critical roles in the success of British colonization. However, it was not valued to have a background in any of these areas of study for a long time. The British did not anticipate much enthusiasm on the part of their Indian colleagues and were hesitant to spend the money necessary to bring over an extra professor to teach geology. H.B. Medlicott, who succeeded Oldham and was also chosen as a professor at Roorkee College, vehemently opposed the establishment of Geology electives. The Indians' supposed lack of intelligence served as an excuse each time.

Furthermore, it was said that the Department only had fifteen graded officers, "a number too small to give any encouragement to the creation of special courses," hence there was no need for special classes. The Governor-General shared these sentiments. As a result, Geological Education languished until 1893, when a chair of Geology was founded at the Presidency College in Calcutta. A few students started taking B.A. exams with Geology as a subject of honor. There was no plan to establish a mining academy until 1904. The INC requested that the Government establish a mining college. Shihpur Engineering College has started offering mining courses as a consolation.

Learning About Medicine

In 1835, efforts to introduce medical knowledge from Europe finally succeeded. Calcutta Medical College was established to replace medical education provided by madrassas and the Sanskrit College. In 1852, the Presidency Surgeon, Dr. Jackson, suggested creating "a Bengalee class of local physicians" at the Medical college. Additionally, in 1852, Madras Medical School began offering college-level classes.

In 1860 the school year, the pupils were separated into four groups: the Primary group, the Apprentice group, the Hindustani group, and the Bengali group. Students in the Primary Class took all five years of their medical education in English. They

were prepared to take the Calcutta University Licence in Medicine and Surgery (LMS), Bachelor of Medicine (M.B.), and Doctor of Medicine (M.D.) exams. In 1864, the Bengali class was split into two tracks: the Native Apothecary track, which prepared students for hospital assistantship, and the Vernacular Licentiate track, which provided more extensive clinical instruction to prepare students for the independent practice among the poor. The military was one of the primary beneficiaries of this kind of segregated educational system.

As "the local medical officer from Bengal and Hindustan failed to earn the faith of Punjabis," there was a need for a medical center to be established in Punjab. To this, the Governor-General admitted, "Most people from Punjab are not interested in attending medical school in Calcutta. As a result, meeting local demand would need providing access to medical training at a Lahore-based institution ". This led to the establishment of the Lahore Medical College in 1859.

The field of medical education has to work under a lot of pressure. Many hopefuls flocked to hospitals and clinics to apply. It's safe to assume that medical schools received an abundance of applications. On the other hand, the issue was insufficient funding and improper incentives. Many students dropped out of school or had to drop out due to financial difficulties. Indeed, at the mofussil institutions, there were not enough educators to fulfill the needs of the students. A lack of laboratory equipment, scholarships, and issues with teaching language worsened the challenges.

Conclusion

From the above, it is clear that the British significantly impacted the development of scientific and technical establishments. Colonial science has dominated India's scientific community. In the subsequent stage, Indians themselves pushed for a western-style scientific education. Later in the 19th century, the concept of National Science became a reality. In response to imperialism, nationalist movements sparked renewed interest in Indian culture and learning. The first institution to be founded with no Europeans in charge but instead by Indians

marked a transition from Colonial Science to National Science.

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